

Oral presentation

Developing of automatic devices mounted on a terrestrial vehicle for field monitoring of CaLsol and implementation of permanent surveillance system of psyllids

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Abstract: A remote-controlled electric robot has been built to inspect the presence of CaLsol in horticultural crops by remote sensing. The devices used in the robot are three different DLSR cameras (one colour and other two modified for to capture NIR and BNDVI images), one thermal camera, one multispectral camera (eight bands between 550 and 850 nm) and one hyperspectral camera (400- 1000 nm). All cameras were placed facing the ground (plants). To prevent the influence of the uncontrolled natural light, the inspection area that was protected from outside light with a canvas and hence four halogen spotlights were used to light the scene. The images captured were georeferenced using a GNSS receiver (resolution of 3 cm). To guide the robot and synchronize the acquisition of images, a customized electronic board was developed using an inductive sensor coupled to the wheels of the robot. A custom software installed on an industrial computer allowed to control the acquisition of the images and the geolocation. During four seasons, monthly inspections have been carried out on several test plots of carrots in Villena (Alicante, Spain) trying to detect asymptomatic plants infected with CaLsol. Along the different seasons, the robot has received several improvements in order to increase its performance. This last year a new thermal camera has been used to solve the problems encountered in previous versions. Also, some errors have been detected and corrected in the geolocation software. Field maps with a high resolution (between 1 and 2.5 mm/pixel) have been created using vegetative indices from the spectral data. During the last trial, 50 plants were tagged to be identified in the images and collected separately to be analysed using real-time PCR. The robot has been effective in inspecting the fields and obtaining valuable remote sensing data. However, the predictive models created from the information obtained by the sensors did not allowed clear results for the early detection of the disease.

On the other hand, a prototype of surveillance station has been created to monitor potential vectors trapped in the field. The device captures and sends images of trapped insects, including potential vectors of CaLsol, to a remote server for the further inspection of an entomologist. The device was created on the basis of a Raspberry PI platform and incorporates a camera to capture the images, a control board to program the intervals of image capture and a modem to send the images and additional information to a remote server via 3G. The device can be programmed to capture and send the images at certain times of the day. A solar panel allows to power the devices for several weeks without the need of being recharged. The implementation has been carried out on Irwin type traps, consisting of a ceramic tile with a rough texture and a color and reflection spectrum similar to that of the leaves of the plant. The tile is placed horizontally inside a transparent methacrylate box at a height similar to that of the culture that is filled with a 50% solution of ethylene glycol water. The insects are attracted by the reflection of the tile and are trapped in the liquid. After several previous versions, the device have been fully redesigned and are being tested in the carrot test field in Villena. The devices have been programmed to send images of the insects trapped every three hours, and also the temperature of the field, to a remote server. In addition, a customised software has been developed to facilitate the analysis of the insects present in the images of the traps.